

Breakdown of Excluded Studies after Selection Process

Of the 1,117 excluded studies, a substantial share focused on transport and mobility systems (22.8%) (Huang *et al.*, 2010; Fernández *et al.*, 2022; Yin *et al.*, 2025) or on structural engineering topics (12.9%) (Penadés-Plà *et al.*, 2019; Miguel *et al.*, 2022; Aoki *et al.*, 2024). Additional exclusions comprised studies centered on urban planning and real estate markets (9.4%) (Yang *et al.*, 2020; Dorignon *et al.*, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2025), energy and environmental systems (7.0%) (Bianchini and Hewage, 2012; Mokhtara *et al.*, 2021; Dong *et al.*, 2024), and geotechnical or hydrology engineering (4.1%) (Anibas *et al.*, 2011; Brunetti *et al.*, 2017; Yaychi *et al.*, 2024). A smaller proportion of studies (2.8%) addressed construction management topics that focused on organizational, contractual, or operational issues rather than cost estimation or cost modeling (Dyer *et al.*, 2012; Kang *et al.*, 2013; Franz *et al.*, 2022). A limited subset of studies (1.9%) examined construction cost-related topics without considering spatial modeling or missing locally observed cost data contexts (Choi *et al.*, 2016; Lee and Yun, 2024), which are central to the scope of this review. The remaining studies (39.1%) were excluded because they addressed engineering domains outside the construction field, such as computational optimization (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2022) and communication systems (Pham *et al.*, 2010; Koziel and Pietrenko-Dabrowska, 2019).

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